

COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF ELECTRONIC-BASED GOVERNMENT SYSTEM (SPBE) IN INDONESIA: A LITERATURE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The digital transformation of government is one of the important agendas in bureaucratic reform in Indonesia. These efforts are realized through the implementation of the Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE) which aims to improve the effectiveness, efficiency, transparency, and quality of public services. However, the implementation of SPBE does not only depend on technological aspects, but also requires collaboration between various stakeholders involved in the administration of government. This study aims to analyze the implementation of the Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE) in Indonesia through the perspective of Collaborative Governance. The research uses a literature study method with a qualitative approach through the review of various scientific articles, books, regulations, and related documents relevant to SPBE and Collaborative Governance. Data analysis was carried out using content analysis techniques based on the Collaborative Governance framework developed by Ansell and

Gash (2008), including starting conditions, institutional design, facilitative leadership, and collaborative process. The results show that the implementation of SPBE in Indonesia is influenced by the readiness of resources, regulatory support, institutional capacity, and the quality of coordination between agencies. In addition, facilitative leadership, effective communication, and shared commitment are important factors in supporting successful collaboration. Collaborative Governance contributes to improving the integration of public services, strengthening institutional coordination, and supporting the realization of a more effective digital transformation of government. This study concludes that the success of SPBE implementation is not only determined by technological readiness, but also by the ability of various actors to build sustainable collaboration to realize better governance.

Keywords: Collaborative Governance, Electronic-Based Government System, SPBE, Digital Transformation, Public Administration.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of information and communication technology has encouraged a paradigm shift in the administration of government in various countries. Digital transformation is no longer understood as limited to the use of technology to support government administration,

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but has developed into a strategic instrument in improving bureaucratic effectiveness, quality of public services, transparency, and government accountability (Nam & Pardo, 2011; Meijer & Bolívar, 2016). In the Indonesian context, efforts to digitally transform government are realized through the implementation of the Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE) which aims to create integrated, efficient, and public service-oriented governance.

The implementation of SPBE obtained a legal basis through Presidential Regulation Number 95 of 2018 concerning Electronic-Based Government Systems. This policy directs all government agencies to integrate business processes, data, applications, and information technology infrastructure to improve the quality of government administration. SPBE is also an important part of the national bureaucratic reform agenda which emphasizes the importance of digital transformation as a means of realizing effective, transparent, and accountable governance.

However, the implementation of SPBE in Indonesia still faces various challenges. Several studies show that the integration of information systems between agencies has not run optimally, the capacity of human resources in the field of information technology is still uneven, and coordination between regional apparatus organizations often faces various institutional obstacles. Research on the implementation of SPBE in Bireuen Regency shows that the collaboration built in the implementation of SPBE has not been fully effective. Facilitative leadership and institutional design are still not optimal, while the integration of digital service applications between regional apparatus is still running separately. In addition, community participation in the collaboration process has also not taken place actively (Syidky, 2025). This condition shows that the success of SPBE implementation does not only depend on technological readiness, but also is influenced by the ability of actors to build effective cooperation and coordination.

In modern public administration, the complexity of government problems can no longer be solved through a hierarchical bureaucratic approach. The implementation of public policies, especially those related to digital transformation, requires the involvement of various actors who have different resources, authority, and interests. Therefore, *the Collaborative Governance* approach becomes relevant to explain how governments, the private sector, academia, and society can work together in achieving common goals (Ansell & Gash, 2008).

The importance of collaboration in the digital transformation of government is also seen in the implementation of smart cities in Indonesia. Research by Bilqis et al. (2025) shows that the success of digital public service innovation is greatly influenced by the quality of collaborative governance that connects the government, the private sector, academia, and civil society. Clear collaboration structures, facilitative leadership, and effective communication have been proven to improve the responsiveness, transparency, and adaptability of digital public services (Bilqis et al., 2025). On the other hand, sectoral egos, human resource capacity gaps, and infrastructure limitations are still the main challenges in realizing effective digital transformation.

Research on SPBE in Indonesia so far has mostly focused on the evaluation of the SPBE index, the quality of electronic-based public services, the digital transformation of bureaucracy, and the implementation of SPBE in certain agencies or regions. Meanwhile, research that specifically examines the implementation of SPBE through the perspective of *Collaborative Governance* is still relatively limited. Most of the research focuses more on the technology and system management aspects rather than the dynamics of collaboration between actors which are important factors in the successful implementation of SPBE.

In addition, previous research generally uses a case study approach to produce findings that are contextual in a specific area. Until now, there is still limited research that synthesizes various research results related to the implementation of SPBE in Indonesia to understand how collaboration is built, the actors involved, the supporting factors, and the challenges faced in the

implementation process. This condition shows that there is a research *gap* that needs further attention.

Based on this description, this study aims to analyze the implementation of the Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE) in Indonesia through the perspective of *Collaborative Governance*. This study seeks to identify the actors involved in the implementation of SPBE, the forms of collaboration developed, the supporting and inhibiting factors of collaboration, and the contribution of *Collaborative Governance* in supporting the success of the government's digital transformation. Through a literature study approach, this research is expected to contribute to the development of public administration studies, especially those related to collaborative governance and digital transformation of government in Indonesia.

Before entering into the theoretical discussion, it is important to identify the position of this research compared to previous research. The following table shows that most of the research still focuses on the implementation of SPBE at the regional level or the digital transformation of public services, while studies that specifically synthesize the implementation of SPBE through the *perspective of Collaborative Governance* are still relatively limited.

Table 1. Research Gap Penelitian

Researcher	Research Focus	Key Findings	Research Weaknesses
Syidky (2025)	Collaborative Governance in the implementation of SPBE in Bireuen Regency	Inter-agency collaboration affects the implementation of SPBE	Focus on one region so that it does not yet describe national conditions
Bilqis et al. (2025)	Collaborative Governance in Smart Cities	Collaborative governance supports digital public service transformation	Does not specifically discuss SPBE
Mursalim (2017)	Implementation of E-Government in Indonesia	Digitalization improves the quality of public services	Not using the Collaborative Governance perspective
Primary (2020)	SPBE and Bureaucratic Reform	SPBE supports bureaucratic efficiency	Focus on administrative and technological aspects
Various SPBE studies	Evaluation of the SPBE index and digitization of public services	Explain the maturity level of SPBE	Has not studied the pattern of collaboration between actors comprehensively

Source: Processed Author (2026).

Based on previous research, it can be seen that the implementation of SPBE is generally studied from the aspects of technology, public services, and bureaucratic reform. Meanwhile, research that examines the implementation of SPBE through the perspective of *Collaborative Governance* is still limited, especially research that synthesizes various research results to understand collaboration patterns, actors involved, supporting factors, and challenges of SPBE implementation in Indonesia. Therefore, this study seeks to fill the gap through a literature review approach using the *Collaborative Governance* theory developed by Ansell and Gash (2008).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Collaborative Governance

The concept of *Collaborative Governance* developed in response to the increasingly complex public problems that cannot be solved by the government independently. Ansell and Gash (2008) define *Collaborative Governance* as a governance arrangement in which one or more public institutions directly involve non-governmental stakeholders in a collective decision-making process that is formal, consensus-oriented, and aims to implement or formulate public policies. According to Ansell and Gash (2008), the success of collaboration is influenced by several main components which include *starting conditions*, *institutional design*, *facilitative leadership*, and *collaborative processes*.

The *Collaborative Governance* approach emphasizes the importance of the involvement of various actors in the administration of government. Collaboration involves not only the government, but also the private sector, academics, civil society organizations, and the community as users of public services. Through collaboration, various resources, knowledge, and capacity can be combined to produce more effective public policies and services (Ansell & Gash, 2008).

In the context of digital transformation of government, *Collaborative Governance* is important because the implementation of digital policies requires cross-sector integration, inter-agency coordination, and the involvement of various stakeholders. Bilqis et al. (2025) explain that collaborative governance plays an important role in supporting the development of digital-based public services through the formation of effective communication, institutional coordination, and strengthening community participation (Bilqis et al., 2025).

Ansell and Gash's Collaborative Governance Model (2008)

Ansell and Gash (2008) explain that the success of *Collaborative Governance* is influenced by four main components:

1. **Starting Conditions** are the initial conditions that affect the collaboration process, such as resource inequality, the history of relationships between actors, and the level of trust that has been formed.
2. **Institutional Design**, refers to the rules, procedures, organizational structure, and coordination mechanisms that govern the collaboration process.
3. **Facilitative Leadership**, shows the role of leaders in facilitating communication, building trust, and resolving conflicts between actors.
4. **Collaborative Process** is an interaction process that includes face-to-face dialogue, *trust building*, commitment to the process, *shared understanding*, and *achieving intermediate outcomes*.

This framework is used as an analytical tool in research to understand the implementation of SPBE through the perspective of inter-stakeholder collaboration.

Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE)

The Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE) is a government implementation that utilizes information and communication technology to provide services to SPBE users in an integrated manner. SPBE was developed as an instrument of bureaucratic reform aimed at improving the quality of governance and public services through the use of digital technology.

The implementation of SPBE in Indonesia obtained a legal basis through Presidential Regulation Number 95 of 2018 concerning Electronic-Based Government Systems. The regulation emphasizes that the implementation of SPBE must be carried out in an integrated manner to increase the efficiency, effectiveness, transparency, and accountability of government administration.

The implementation of SPBE covers various aspects, including digital governance, data integration, application interoperability, information security, and digitization of public services. The success of SPBE implementation does not only depend on technological readiness, but also on organizational capacity, the quality of human resources, and the ability of various actors to build effective coordination (Syidky, 2025).

Research Thinking Framework

[Source: Processed by the Author based on Ansell & Gash \(2008\), 2026.](#)

This study uses *the Collaborative Governance* theory from Ansell and Gash (2008) to analyze the implementation of SPBE in Indonesia. The successful implementation of SPBE is seen not only as a result of technological and regulatory readiness, but also as the result of a collaborative process involving various stakeholders.

In this study, the implementation of SPBE is analyzed through four main dimensions of *Collaborative Governance*, namely *starting conditions*, *institutional design*, *facilitative leadership*, and *collaborative process*. These four dimensions are used to identify supporting factors, obstacles, and collaboration dynamics that affect the success of SPBE implementation in Indonesia.

3. METHODS

This study uses a *literature study* method with a qualitative approach. This method is used to review and analyze various literature related to *Collaborative Governance* and the

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implementation of Electronic-Based Government Systems (SPBE) in Indonesia. Literature studies are chosen because they allow researchers to gain a comprehensive understanding of concepts, developments, and various research findings relevant to the research topic.

The data used is secondary data derived from scientific journal articles, books, laws and regulations, and official government documents related to SPBE and *Collaborative Governance*. The literature was obtained through searching on Google Scholar, Garuda, SINTA, and various other scientific sources using keywords such as *Collaborative Governance*, *Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE)*, *Digital Government*, and *E-Government*.

Data analysis is carried out using content *analysis* techniques, namely by identifying, grouping, and interpreting various information obtained from the literature that has been collected. The analysis was carried out based on the *Collaborative Governance* framework developed by Ansell and Gash (2008), which includes *starting conditions*, *institutional design*, *facilitative leadership*, and *collaborative process*. Through these stages, this study seeks to explain the role of *Collaborative Governance* in supporting the implementation of SPBE in Indonesia.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

***Starting Conditions* in SPBE Implementation in Indonesia**

In the perspective of *Collaborative Governance*, *starting conditions* are the initial conditions that affect the success of collaboration between actors (Ansell & Gash, 2008). The implementation of the Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE) in Indonesia is motivated by the need to improve the quality of governance through the use of information and communication technology. The development of digital technology and public demands for fast, transparent, and accountable public services encourage the government to carry out digital transformation in the administration of government.

However, the implementation of SPBE in various regions shows that there is a difference in resource capacity and institutional readiness. Some government agencies already have adequate digital infrastructure, while others still face limitations in technological facilities, human resources, and budget support. Syidky's research (2025) shows that the implementation of SPBE still faces obstacles in the form of suboptimal system integration, limited organizational capacity, and low involvement of various stakeholders in the digital service development process. This condition is the initial factor that affects the effectiveness of collaboration in the implementation of SPBE. In addition, the digital transformation of government is also marked by an increasing need for coordination between agencies because the implementation of SPBE cannot be carried out by one organization independently. This complexity requires more intensive cooperation between the central government, local governments, technical agencies, and other supporting parties.

***Institutional Design* in SPBE Implementation**

Institutional design refers to the rules, procedures, and institutional structures that are the basis for the implementation of collaboration (Ansell & Gash, 2008). In the implementation of SPBE, institutional aspects are an important factor because digital transformation requires system integration involving various government organizations. The Government of Indonesia has established various regulations as the basis for the implementation of SPBE, one of which is through Presidential Regulation Number 95 of 2018 concerning Electronic-Based Government

Systems. The regulation regulates the implementation of SPBE in an integrated manner with the aim of increasing government efficiency, effectiveness, transparency, and accountability.

Although a regulatory framework is available, various studies show that the implementation of SPBE still faces challenges in institutional coordination. Some agencies still run information systems separately, thus hindering the integration of data and public services. This condition shows that the success of SPBE implementation does not only depend on the existence of regulations, but also on the ability of government institutions to build effective coordination mechanisms between organizations.

In the context of *Collaborative Governance*, clear institutional design plays an important role in creating certainty of roles, responsibilities, and cooperation mechanisms between actors involved in the implementation of SPBE.

Facilitative Leadership in SPBE Implementation

The success of collaboration is inseparable from the existence of leadership that is able to facilitate communication and coordination between actors. Ansell and Gash (2008) emphasized that *facilitative leadership* functions as a driver of collaboration through building trust, resolving conflicts, and strengthening mutual commitment. In the implementation of SPBE in Indonesia, the role of leadership can be seen through the involvement of the central government in formulating policies, developing implementation standards, and evaluating the implementation of SPBE in government agencies. Leadership also plays a role in encouraging system integration, strengthening cross-sector coordination, and ensuring that each agency has the same commitment to supporting digital transformation.

Syidky's research (2025) shows that facilitative leadership is one of the important factors in building collaboration on SPBE implementation. Leadership that is able to encourage communication and cooperation between agencies contributes to increasing the effectiveness of SPBE implementation. On the contrary, weak coordination and dominance of certain actors have the potential to hinder the collaboration process. Thus, the successful implementation of SPBE requires leadership that is not only oriented to administrative aspects, but also able to be a facilitator in building collaboration between stakeholders.

Collaborative Process in SPBE Implementation

According to Ansell and Gash (2008), the collaborative process is the core of *Collaborative Governance*. This process includes dialogue, *trust building*, commitment to common goals, and the development of *shared understanding*. The implementation of SPBE requires continuous interaction between various actors because the implementation of digital governance involves many sectors and organizations. Collaboration is realized through coordination between government agencies, integration of data and applications, the preparation of digital service standards, and the development of interconnected information systems.

Research by Bilqis et al. (2025) shows that effective communication and the participation of various stakeholders are important factors in supporting the success of the government's digital transformation. Good collaboration is able to improve the quality of public services, strengthen transparency, and encourage innovation in the implementation of digital government (Bilqis et al., 2025). However, the collaboration process still faces various obstacles, such as sectoral egos, differences in organizational capacity, limited human resources, and low integration of information systems. These obstacles show that building trust and mutual commitment is still a challenge in the implementation of SPBE in Indonesia.

Table 2. Supporting and Inhibiting Factors for SPBE Implementation

Supporting Factors	Inhibiting Factors
SPBE Regulation	Sectoral ego
Leadership commitment	Limitations of digital HR
Technology support	Infrastructure is not even
Cross-agency coordination	System integration is not yet optimal
Bureaucratic transformation	Budget constraints

[Source: Processed Author \(2026\).](#)

Contribution of Collaborative Governance to the Implementation of SPBE in Indonesia

Table 3. SPBE Implementation Analysis Based on the Collaborative Governance Dimension

Dimensions	Findings
Starting Conditions	There is a gap in human resource and infrastructure capacity
Institutional Design	SPBE regulation supports service integration
Facilitative Leadership	Leadership strengthens cross-agency coordination
Collaborative Process	Communication and commitment are key factors for success

[Source: Processed Author \(2026\).](#)

The results of the literature review show that *Collaborative Governance* has an important role in supporting the successful implementation of SPBE in Indonesia. Through collaboration, various government agencies can integrate resources, information, and organizational capacity to achieve common goals in the digital transformation of government. Collaboration also contributes to increasing the effectiveness of public services through the integration of information systems and simplification of administrative processes. In addition, the implementation of SPBE supported by collaborative governance is able to increase transparency and accountability because the public service process can be carried out in a more open and measurable manner. From the perspective of public administration, *Collaborative Governance* not only functions as a coordination mechanism between organizations, but also becomes a strategic instrument in realizing an integrated digital government. Therefore, strengthening collaboration between agencies, increasing the capacity of human resources, and developing more effective coordination mechanisms are important steps in supporting the successful implementation of SPBE in Indonesia.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

Based on the results of a literature study, the implementation of the Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE) in Indonesia is an important part of the digital transformation of government which aims to improve the effectiveness, efficiency, transparency, and quality of public services. The implementation of SPBE does not only depend on the use of information and communication technology, but also requires synergy and collaboration between various stakeholders involved in the administration of government.

The analysis using the *perspective of Collaborative Governance* shows that the success of SPBE implementation is influenced by several key factors. In terms of *starting conditions*, the implementation of SPBE still faces challenges in the form of differences in resource capacity, digital infrastructure readiness, and organizational ability to manage digital transformation. In

terms of *institutional design*, the existence of SPBE regulations and policies has provided a clear foundation for the implementation of digital governance, although coordination and integration between agencies is still a challenge that needs to be strengthened.

Furthermore, *the facilitative leadership* aspect shows that leadership has an important role in encouraging coordination, building commitment, and facilitating cooperation between actors in the implementation of SPBE. Meanwhile, the *collaborative process* aspect shows that communication, trust, participation, and mutual commitment are factors that determine the success of collaboration in supporting the digital transformation of government.

The results of the study also show that *Collaborative Governance* contributes to increasing the effectiveness of SPBE implementation through strengthening coordination between agencies, integrating public services, and optimizing the use of resources owned by each actor. Thus, the implementation of SPBE cannot be understood solely as a technological transformation, but as a collaborative process involving various parties in realizing better governance.

Suggestions

Based on the results of the research, there are several recommendations that can be considered to increase the effectiveness of SPBE implementation in Indonesia. First, the government needs to strengthen coordination and integration mechanisms between agencies to reduce information system fragmentation and increase interoperability of digital services. Strengthening coordination is important to support the creation of an integrated digital government system that is oriented to the needs of the community.

Second, increasing the capacity of human resources needs to be a major concern in the implementation of SPBE. The development of digital competencies of state civil servants through education, training, and strengthening the digital work culture is an important factor in supporting the success of the government's digital transformation. Third, the government needs to encourage the involvement of various stakeholders, including the private sector, academia, and the community, in the process of developing and implementing SPBE. Broader participation can strengthen innovation, improve service quality, and support the creation of more collaborative governance.

Fourth, strengthening facilitative leadership at various levels of government needs to continue so that the collaboration process can run effectively. Leadership that is able to build communication, resolve conflicts, and encourage mutual commitment will be an important factor in the successful implementation of SPBE.

Finally, further research is recommended to conduct an empirical study on the implementation of SPBE at the ministry, local government, or specific agency levels using case study approaches and mixed *methods*. The research is expected to provide a more in-depth picture of the dynamics of *Collaborative Governance* in the practice of implementing digital governance in Indonesia.

6. BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Ansell, C., & Gash, A. (2008). Collaborative governance in theory and practice. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 18(4), 543-571.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jopart/mum032>

- Bilqis, N., Alhadi, Z., & Putera, R. E. (2025). Collaborative governance in the implementation of smart cities as digital public service innovations in Indonesia. *Journal of Political and Social Sciences (JIPSK)*, 7(1), 1-15.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Emerson, K., Nabatchi, T., & Balogh, S. (2012). An integrative framework for collaborative governance. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 22(1), 1-29. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jopart/mur011>
- Feradiyah, D., & Prianto, A. (2024). Strengthening the role of the government through collaborative governance in providing inclusive jobs in Pasuruan Regency. *Journal of Public*, 7(3), 1077-1093. <https://doi.org/10.35817/publicuho.v7i3.459>
- Fitriyah, N. (2025). Agrarian conflict and land dispute resolution dynamics in Alastlogo Village, Pasuruan Regency. *Journal of Agrarian and Land*, 12(1), 45-58.
- Gash, C. A. (2008). Collaborative Governance in Theory and Practice. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 18(4), 543-571.
- Meijer, A., & Bolívar, M. P. R. (2016). Governing the smart city: A review of the literature on smart urban governance. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 82(2), 392-408. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020852314564308>
- Mursalim, S. W. (2017). Implementation of smart city policy in the city of Bandung. *Journal of Administrative Sciences*, 14(1), 126-138.
- Nam, T., & Pardo, T. A. (2011). Conceptualizing smart city with dimensions of technology, people, and institutions. In *Proceedings of the 12th Annual International Digital Government Research Conference* (pp. 282-291). ACM.
- Pratama, A. B. (2020). The landscape of public service innovation in Indonesia: A comprehensive analysis. *Innovation & Management Review*, 17(1), 25-40. <https://doi.org/10.1108/INMR-11-2018-0080>
- Republic of Indonesia. (2018). *Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 95 of 2018 concerning Electronic-Based Government Systems*. State Secretariat of the Republic of Indonesia.
- Syidky, M. (2025). Government collaboration in the implementation of an electronic-based government system (SPBE) in Bireuen Regency. *Journal of Public Administration*, 12(1), 45-60.
- United Nations. (2024). *United Nations E-Government Survey 2024: Accelerating digital transformation for sustainable development*. United Nations.
- World Bank. (2023). *Digital government and public sector modernization*. World Bank Publications.